

CREATION OF SCENARIO OF EVENTS BASED ON THE NATURE OF CULTURAL EVENTS

Tojiakhmedova Muyassarkhon Khaydarovna
Teacher of Namangan state university
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10984601>

MADANIY TADBIRLAR TURLARI XUSUSIYATIDAN KELIB CHIQUIB TADBIRLAR SENARIYSINI YARATILISHI

Tojiahmedova Muyassarxon Xaydarovna
Namangan davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi

СОЗДАНИЕ СЦЕНАРИЕВ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ИСХОДЯ ИЗ ХАРАКТЕРА КУЛЬТУРНЫХ СОБЫТИЙ

Таджиахмедова Муяссархан Хайдаровна
Преподаватель Наманганского государственного университета

Annotation: This article provides detailed information on script writing methods, instructions for organizing a cultural event, creation of event scenarios based on the characteristics of cultural events.

Keywords: mass cultural event script, script, types of script, movie script, circus script, radio script, television script.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada senariy yozish usullari, madaniy tadbir tashkil etish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar, madaniy tadbir turlari xususiyatidan kelib chiqib tadbirlar senariysini yaratilishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kalit so'zlar: ommaviy madaniy tadbir senariysi, senariy, ssenariy turlari, kino senariy, sirk senariysi, radio senariysi, televizion senariy.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о методах написания сценария, инструкции по организации культурного мероприятия, созданию сценариев мероприятия с учетом особенностей культурного мероприятия.

Ключевые слова: Ключевые слова: сценарий культурно-массового мероприятия, сценарий, виды сценария, сценарий фильма, сценарий цирка, сценарий радио, сценарий телевидения.

Reforms, plans and programs, practical efforts in various fields developed by our head of state and consistently implemented in life are all for man, his interests, comfortable life, safety and fulfillment of dreams, in a word, man and aimed at ensuring his happy life. This country and its people, which amaze the world in the fields of politics, science, culture, art, religion, and its people, due to independence, restore traditions and values, enrich and develop them based on the requirements of the times, realize their identity, and receive a decent education from the world community. is realizing great goals such as taking over. Poetic works created by representatives of classical literature are highly valued by our people as examples of high creativity [1]. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of

normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts [2]. In particular, on May 30, 2019 “On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21, 2020 [3], “On measures to further increasing the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD-4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [4], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” of April 21, 2020, No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time” of April 20, 2021, Decree No. PD-6208 of. Great achievements and results achieved in a short period of time in history - glorified the fame of our homeland, our people, our rich history, our priceless national values and traditions, and our powerful spiritual and economic potential to the whole world.[5]

Scenarios are divided into a number of types depending on the types of cultural and educational events and the purpose of the activity, and each of them has its own characteristics.

If we analyze the term script here, the word “Scenariy” is derived from the Italian word, according to U. Karaboyev in his book “Artistic and public events”, and means “the plan, scheme of the work”. In the dictionaries, the script:

- 1) screenplay;
- 2) the plan of the dramatic work performed in the theater, the plot line, the description of the dramatic movement in the opera, in the ballet - a perfect description of the subject including all the dances and mimes;
- 3) it is explained that the time and order of the participants in the play are shown in the 1st guide.[6]

Khaidar Mukhammad writes in his book “The Skill of Screenwriting” that the term “Screenwriter” was created and introduced by taking the word “Screenwriter” from the Persian “Navosanda” meaning writer, writer, and writer. In this book, the author has provided valuable information on the scenario of television, film and theatrical performances.

In other sources – “Scenario” (“Scenario” in Italian means “literary-dramatic work”) is a literary description of the content of the event, in which, based on a serious sequence, the theme and idea, which are the elements of action, a it is written that transition from fragment to binary, blocks, decorations, texts are fully displayed. But in any case, it is appropriate to describe that the script is a complete written description of the events, celebrations and performances.

The following tasks are performed during script writing:

- the venue of the event is studied;
- the idea of the topic and event originated from the local conditions resources are sought without;
- documentary materials are artisticized;[7]

Associate Professor V. Rustamov, a specialist in the organization of public cultural events, said that directing has many specialties (for example, theater directing, television directing, radio

directing, puppet theater directing, public holidays and performances such as directing, etc.) the screenplay is also divided into several types according to their specialties and nature.

The peculiarity of the organization of public events and performances is that they are held in non-standard, non-standard spaces, and there should be a “stage in a box” in it. It is not difficult to understand that it is an area that requires a serious approach, which is characterized by the lack of equipment, the lack of special skills of its participants, the large number of participants and other aspects.[8] The most difficult aspect is the absence of a ready-made dramatic source, as in staging a play. When writing a script for the events held in the fields, it is a process that requires a special skill for the screenwriter to understand the director’s opinion, his point of view, and to fully use the tools that give meaning to the field.

Currently, scenarios are being written for the organization of scientific conferences. An example of this is the lectures held at the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan. Such events are called scientific and educational events.

A vivid example of this is the program prepared for the video selector (conference) on the topic “Reading culture” held by professors and teachers of UzDSMI for all higher education institutions.[9] For such events, the scenario is not completely written, but the scenario program is prepared. (Lectures and other materials within the program are submitted based on the required forms).

Any program should be short and concise, covering all aspects of the process.

Another one of the scientific conferences are lectures. Lectures are held in the form of lectures and opinions of scientists on a specific topic. Lectorium - (Krt. lectorium, German: Lettner) - a high wooden pulpit placed during worship in ancient Catholic churches. Lectures appeared in Italy in the XI century, and later in Germany and France. Currently, lectures are more related to scientific events, where scientific opinions are exchanged based on a certain topic. Such activities have a great impact on increasing the scientific potential of people, expanding their worldviews, and increasing their knowledge. Being clear about the types and genres of events makes it easier to create a scenario. Because the screenwriter does not get distracted when working on a specific genre, he follows a clear, straight path. It is worth mentioning that each event has its own procedure (procedure, work steps, requirements) that requires a unique approach. Its dramatic basis, and these features and requirements must be taken into account when creating a script. In conclusion, it can be said that the program of each event should be prepared in a way that is thorough, clear and understandable to everyone.

References:

1. TOJIAKHMEDOVA MUYASSAR. THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 – 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021. 85-87 pp.
2. Mirhakimova F. Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY. – 2022. <https://scienceweb.uz/publication/4566>
3. Topildiev Odiljon Rakhimjonovich, Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. REFORM IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. Web of scientist:

International scientific research journal. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 5, May., 2022.196-198 pp.

4. Mirhakimova, F. K. (2021). The state museum of history and culture of Namangan region past and today. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(8), 84-89.
5. Tojiakhmedova Muyassarkhon Khaydarovna. MAIN STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF WORLD AND NATIONAL CINEMATOGRAPHY. GOSPODARKA I INNOWACJE. Volume: 21.2022.59-61 pp.
6. Rizayev Sh. Spirituality of the scene. – Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2000. – P. 17.
7. Sayfullaev B.S., Mamatkasimov J.A. Acting skills. – Tashkent: Science and technology, 2012. –P. 388. 10. Sayfullaev B. History and theory of performing arts. – Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2014. – P. 12.
8. Egamberdiyev F.T. Direction of pop and public shows. – Tashkent: Science and Technology, 2018. – P. 36.
9. Usmanov R.I. Director. – Tashkent: Science, 1997. – P. 22.